

Core regions in immunoglobulin heavy chain enhancers essential for survival of non-Hodgkin lymphoma cells identified by a CRISPR interference screen

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Authors contribution

MEK, WS: Investigation, Data analysis, Writing, Figure and table preparation; MP, MK, WŁ, AS: Investigation; TW: Data analysis; JEJG, AD, JK, AvdB, NR: Project conceptualization, providing materials and samples; ADK: Project conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Data analysis, Writing. All authors read and approved the manuscript.

Data availability

Raw and processed RNA-seq data have been deposited in Gene Expression Omnibus (GSE247393, token for reviewer's access: iryfqusaxpgrtmz).

Declaration of competing interest

None of the authors have a conflict of interest.

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Abstract

Chromosomal translocations in non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL) result in activation of oncogenes by placing them under the regulation of immunoglobulin heavy chain (IGH) super-enhancers. Aberrant expression of translocated oncogenes induced by enhancer activity can contribute to lymphomagenesis. The role of the *IGH* enhancers in normal B-cell development is well established, but knowledge regarding the precise mechanisms of their involvement in control of the translocated oncogenes is limited. The goal of this project was to define the critical regions in the *IGH* regulatory elements and identify enhancer RNAs (eRNA). We designed a sgRNA library densely covering the *IGH* enhancers and performed tiling CRISPR interference screens in three NHL cell lines. This revealed three regions crucial for NHL cell growth. With chromatin-enriched RNA-Seq we showed transcription from the core enhancer regions and subsequently validated expression of the eRNAs in a large panel of NHL cell lines and tissue samples. Inhibition of the essential *IGH* enhancer regions decreased expression of eRNAs and translocated oncogenes in several NHL cell lines. The observed expression and growth patterns were consistent with the breakpoints in the *IGH* locus. Moreover, targeting the E μ enhancer resulted in loss of B-cell receptor expression. In a Burkitt lymphoma cell line, MYC overexpression partially rescued the phenotype induced by *IGH* enhancer inhibition. Our results indicated the most critical regions in the *IGH* enhancers and provided new insights into the current understanding of the role of *IGH* enhancers in B-cell NHL. As such, this study forms a basis for development of potential therapeutic approaches.

Keywords: IGH, enhancer, lymphoma, CRISPR/Cas9, BCR, MYC, BCL2

Introduction

Non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) account for 3% of all cancer cases worldwide^{1,2}. They arise from B cells at various stages of maturation, which is a multistep process involving several rearrangements occurring at the immunoglobulin heavy chain (*IGH*) locus. Obligatory intermediates during rearrangement of the *IGH* locus are DNA-double strand breaks. These breaks can result in illegitimate recombination and various chromosomal translocations including the t(8;14)(q24;q32) *MYC/IGH* in Burkitt lymphoma (BL) and t(14;18)(q32;q21) *IGH/BCL2* in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) and follicular lymphoma³. As a result, the translocated oncogene is placed under the control of *IGH* enhancers, which leads to its overexpression. *MYC* is a transcription factor involved in many processes such as proliferation, apoptosis, DNA-damage response⁴. *BCL2* suppresses cell death by preventing the activation of caspases which contributes to treatment resistance and poor prognosis⁵. Interestingly, oncogenic translocation itself may not be sufficient to drive lymphomagenesis⁶, yet can contribute to instability that can in turn lead to accumulation of other mutations and malignant transformation⁷. The activity of the *IGH* locus is governed by enhancers: E μ (the intronic enhancer) and 3' regulatory regions (3'RR1 and 3'RR2, Figure 1A)⁸. Among others, the feature of active enhancers is expression of enhancer RNAs (eRNAs). This class of non-coding RNAs was regarded as a by-product of an active transcription machinery, but increasing evidence shows that eRNAs can be functional⁹. Active transcription of 3'RR in activated B cells was first demonstrated by Peron et al¹⁰. Recently, the eRNA ARIEL was found to be a driver of oncogenesis in T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia¹¹. In BL, the eRNA AL928768.3, expressed from 3'RR1, was shown to downregulate *MYC* expression upon knockdown¹². Nevertheless, knowledge regarding the role of eRNAs in NHL remains limited.

The function of *IGH* enhancers has been extensively studied in normal B-cells. These studies showed that E μ is important for earlier stages of B-cell development, mainly VDJ recombination¹³, while 3'RR takes over the locus control at later stages, namely SHM and CSR¹⁴. Several mouse models demonstrated the involvement of *IGH* enhancers in regulation of oncogene expression and lymphomagenesis, but still more research is necessary to understand these processes in malignant human B-cells, where the *IGH* enhancers organization differs from mouse¹⁵. As *IGH* enhancers encompass a region of approximately 64 kb in total, it is important to pinpoint the core regions crucial for lymphoma cells.

The CRISPR/Cas9 system can be applied to study tissue-specific *cis*-regulatory elements of enhancers¹⁶. Here, we employed tiling CRISPR/dCas9-KRAB screen to pinpoint the critical regions within E μ and 3'RRs in BL and DLBCL cell lines. RNA-seq of chromatin-enriched RNAs revealed transcriptional activity of *IGH* enhancers, which we also confirmed in primary patient samples. Further validation in several NHL

cell lines revealed various patterns of dependency on *IGH* enhancers reflecting the differences in breakpoint location. The underlying molecular mechanisms involved disturbed expression of translocated oncogenes and in some cases also B-cell receptor (BCR) presentation.

Methods

Cell lines

Burkitt lymphoma: BL41, CA46, DG75 (DSMZ, Braunschweig, Germany), ST486 (ATCC, LGC Standards, Lomianki, Poland), BL2, BL60, JI, LY19 (gift from prof. Reiner Siebert, Ulm University, Germany), diffuse large B-cell lymphoma: SUDHL4, WSU-DLCL2 (DSMZ) and P493-6¹⁷ (gift from prof. D. Eick, Helmholtz Center, Munich, Germany) were grown in RPMI 1640 (Lonza, Basel, Switzerland) and HEK293T (DSMZ) in DMEM (Lonza), supplemented with 2mM L-glutamine, 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin (Biowest, Nuaille, France) and 10-20% fetal bovine serum (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA). Standard conditions: 37°C, 5% CO₂, humidified incubator. Cells were regularly tested for *Mycoplasma* contamination by PCR.

Patient samples

Enhancer RNA expression was validated in patient-derived NHL samples: BL (8 cases, all MYC translocation positive) and DLBCL (14 cases: 6 germinal center B-cell (GCB), 7 activated B-cell (ABC) and 1 unclassified) as well as tonsil tissues obtained during tonsillectomy as controls (6 cases). Tissues were obtained from the Pathology files of the University Medical Center Groningen tissue bank. They were used in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and the protocol was approved by the Medical Ethical Review board of the UMCG (RR#201800554).

Design and generation of the CRISPR-eIGH library

IGH enhancer regions were defined by the H3K27ac plus 5 kb flanking sequences (hg19): E μ (chr14:106317800-106336124), 3'RR1 (chr14:106140100-106181250) and 3'RR2 (chr14:106019800-106055011). Tiling library of sgRNAs covering those regions was designed and cloned into the lentiGuide-Puro vector¹⁸.

CRISPR screen

27.5 x 10⁶ cells stably expressing dCas9-KRAB were transduced in duplicate with CRISPR-eIGH library, with the previously established amount of virus. After four days of selection with puromycin (T0) 8 x 10⁶ cells were collected for DNA isolation. Remaining cells were further cultured for 20 population

doublings. At each passage, the number of cells corresponding to 1,000x coverage of the library, that is 8×10^6 , were cultured in RPMI medium with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (DG75) or 0.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (other cell lines) puromycin and collected at the final timepoint (T1).

Chromatin-enriched RNA-Seq and data analysis

RNA from chromatin fraction was sent for RNA-Seq stranded library preparation, pair-end sequencing and bioinformatic data analysis to Novogene (Beijing, China). Sequencing was performed on Illumina X-Ten platform. Quality control of raw data in FASTQ format was performed, clean data were obtained by removing reads containing adapter and poly-N sequences and reads with low quality. Approximately $77\text{-}92 \times 10^6$ clean reads were obtained per sample. All downstream analyses were based on clean data with high quality. Reads were mapped to the human reference genome version GRCh37.87 using HISAT 2 software. Reads mapping to the *IGH* enhancer regions (see **Design of the CRISPR-eIGH library**) were selected for further study. Using Galaxy¹⁹ BAM files provided by Novogene were sliced by genomic region chr14:106019800-106337000 and filtered by second mate to retrieve information about the strand from which the transcript was derived. Next, using Integrative Genome Browser²⁰, BedGraph files were generated and visualized in UCSC Genome Browser (<http://genome.ucsc.edu>)²¹.

Results

Generation of the CRISPR-eIGH library targeting *IGH* enhancers

Target regions of the human $E\mu$, 3'RR1 and 3'RR2 were defined by the H3K27ac histone mark in B cells (GM12878 cell line from ENCODE) (Supplementary Figure 1) and a total of 18,732 sgRNAs were designed. Due to homology within the 3'RR1 and 3'RR2 regions, several sgRNAs were present multiple times in the design and sgRNAs targeting up to two sites within the regions of interest were allowed (12,062 sgRNAs remained). Further testing for off-targets elsewhere in the genome excluded 5,080 sgRNAs. The final library included 6,982 sgRNAs that cover the $E\mu$ and 3'RR with an average distance between the sgRNAs of 8 bp for the $E\mu$ and 11 bp for 3'RRs (Figure 1B). 2,344 sgRNAs were common for 3'RR1 and 3'RR2. Including the negative and positive control sgRNAs the final library consisted of 7,971 sgRNAs (Supplementary Table 1).

NGS-based quality control of the CRISPR-eIGH library confirmed its completeness and integrity (Figure 1C). 88.6% of guides matched perfectly and there were no undetected guides. The skew ratio of top 10% to bottom 10% was 1.58. This confirms good quality of the generated CRISPR-eIGH library.

CRISPRi screen identifies elements of *IGH* enhancers essential for lymphoma cell growth

To identify essential elements of *IGH* enhancers, we performed a CRISPR interference screen. (Figure 1D). First, we generated lymphoma cell lines (BL41, DG75, SUDHL4) stably expressing the catalytically inactive Cas9 fused with the repressive KRAB domain (dCas9-KRAB) (Supplementary Figure 2A). These cells were thereafter transduced in duplicate with lentivirus carrying the CRISPR-e*IGH* library. We achieved transduction efficiency between 21.8% and 30.4% and the coverage of 750x-1,045x (Supplementary Figure 2B). Cells were collected at T0 (after puromycin selection) and at T1 (after 20 population doublings) and the abundance of sgRNA constructs was assessed using NGS. In each cell line we identified a few hundreds of sgRNA constructs showing a consistent ≥ 2 -fold depletion in both screen replicates (Figure 2A, Supplementary Table 2). Nontargeting sgRNAs did not show any major effects, while several sgRNAs targeting CD79a and CD79b were depleted as expected.

Using a sliding window approach we identified three essential regions, hereafter called peaks, marked by sgRNAs highly depleted over time (Supplementary Table 3): one E μ -peak – and two peaks in each of 3'RRs: 3'RR-peak1 and 3'RR-peak2 (Figure 2B). The profoundness of depletion varied between cell lines. For the E μ -peak the strongest effect was observed in SUDHL4, with log₂ FC values reaching -1.4, followed by DG75 (log₂ FC -0.8), while in BL41 it did not exceed -0.4. In both 3'RR peaks we observed the strongest effect in DG75 (log₂ FC \sim -2), while BL41 and SUDHL4 showed less depletion (log₂ FC \sim -1). The significant peaks within 3'RRs overlapped with known DNase I hypersensitive sites (HS) HS4 and HS1.2.

We selected two sgRNAs per peak to validate the effect on cell growth in a GFP competition assay in a larger set of BL and DLBCL cell lines. In line with the results of the screen, we observed progressive depletion of BL and DLBCL cells transduced with sgRNA constructs targeting enhancer-essential regions compared to non-targeting controls (Figure 2C-D). The dependency of B-cells on *IGH* enhancers varied between cell lines, which is possibly linked to differences in the location of the breakpoints in *IGH* (Figure 2E). In DG75²², SUDHL4 and WSU-DLCL2²³ the breakpoint occurs in V/D/J region, hence the E μ is involved in the translocation. Accordingly, the strongest effect on survival in SUDHL4 and WSU-DLCL2 was observed upon inhibition of the E μ -peak, while DG75 was very susceptible to blocking of all identified essential *IGH* regions. BL41 and CA46 have a breakpoint within the constant region C α 1²² resulting in E μ exclusion from the *IGH* locus on the translocated allele, and the strongest effect on survival in those cells was observed upon blocking of 3'RR-peak1, followed by 3'RR-peak2 and E μ . ST486 cell line with breakpoint within the switch region μ ²⁴ proved to be the most resistant to blocking of core *IGH* enhancers regions.

Altogether, our CRISPRi screens identified specific regions in the *IGH* enhancers, essential for survival of B-cell lymphoma cells.

Chromatin-enriched RNA-Seq reveals enhancer RNA transcripts from *IGH* enhancers

To identify transcription of eRNAs from the *IGH* locus, we performed cellular fractionation combined with chromatin-enriched RNA-Seq in BL41, DG75, SUDHL4 lymphoma cells and P493-6 along with HEK293T as controls (no *IGH* translocation). This method allows for relatively fast, reproducible and cost-effective enrichment of eRNAs (Supplementary Figure 3A). Proper fractionation was confirmed by RNA agarose gel electrophoresis (Supplementary Figure 3B), and by using appropriate markers on RNA and protein levels (Supplementary Figure 3C-D).

Focusing on transcripts mapping to the *IGH* enhancers, we observed bidirectional transcription from the E μ and 3'RRs (Figure 3A, Supplementary Figures 4-5) in B-lineage cell lines, but not in HEK293T. The significant peaks identified in the CRISPRi screen were also transcriptionally active. In the E μ transcription from the minus strand was 10-fold higher compared to the plus strand, with the highest read counts for BL cell lines. In 3'RR1 transcription rates were comparable from both strands. For the 3'RR2 more reads were mapped to the plus strand especially for BL41 and SUDHL4.

Cellular localization of eRNAs transcribed from core *IGH* enhancers regions was confirmed with RT-qPCR in subcellular fractions (Figure 3B). eRNAs from the E μ -peak and 3'RR-peak2 were enriched in the chromatin, while the 3'RR-peak1 eRNA was enriched in the cytoplasm.

***IGH*-eRNAs expression in B-cell lymphoma cell lines and patient-derived samples**

We verified eRNA expression from the essential *IGH* regions in a panel of B-cell lymphoma cell lines (Figure 3C). We observed statistically significant lower expression of all tested eRNAs in Hodgkin lymphoma cell lines. There were no differences in expression levels between other groups, including ABC and GCB type DLBCLs. In line with NGS results, we observed higher expression from the E μ -peak compared to 3'RR-peaks.

Next we confirmed eRNA expression in patient-derived FFPE samples (Figure 3D), including 8 BL and 13 DLBCL, and 6 tonsils as control. We observed statistically significant higher expression of 3'RRs in BL.

Downstream effects of targeting *IGH* enhancers on the expression of eRNAs, translocated oncogenes and B-cell receptor

Next we determined the effects of inhibition of significant *IGH* peaks on expression of eRNAs, translocated oncogenes and BCR. Targeting of *IGH* enhancers peaks with selected sgRNAs significantly downregulated expression of eRNAs from the respective regions (Figure 4A, Supplementary Figure 6A). In

the BL cell lines BL41 and DG75 blocking of all three *IGH* peaks led to a consistent, up to 50% decrease of MYC transcript level. This was accompanied by reduced protein levels in DG75 (Supplementary Figure 7). In the BL cell line CA46 downregulation of MYC transcript was observed only upon blocking of 3'RRs, but not E μ (Supplementary Figure 6A), while the MYC protein was consistently decreased in all samples (Supplementary Figure 7). ST486, which in GFP assay appeared to be more resistant, did not exhibit downregulation of MYC, neither on RNA nor protein level (Supplementary Figure 6A, Supplementary Figure 7). In DLBCL cell lines SUDHL4 and WSU-DLCL2 BCL2 expression was decreased on both RNA and protein levels in nearly all samples (Figure 4A, Supplementary Figure 6A, Supplementary Figure 7).

Usually, one *IGH* allele is involved in the translocation, while the other allele is productively rearranged and leads to production of secreted immunoglobulins and expression of the BCR on the cell surface (IgM or IgG)²⁵. Throughout their lifetime B-cells, including lymphoma cells, are constantly tested for proper BCR presentation on cell surface²⁵ as their development and survival depend on it. Our CRISPRi approach targets both the translocated and functional *IGH* alleles. Thus, we checked whether silencing *IGH* enhancers with dCas9-KRAB also leads to changes in BCR expression (Supplementary Figure 8). Targeting of the E μ -peak resulted in appearance of an IgM-negative population in BL cell lines BL41 (50% IgM(-)), DG75 (up to 30% IgM(-)) (Figure 4B-C), CA46 (70% IgM(-)), but not in ST486 (Supplementary Figure 6B-C). A similar effect was observed in IgG-expressing DLBCL cell line SUDHL4 with a BCR-negative population reaching 30-40% (Figure 4B-C). In contrast to the E μ -peak, targeting of the 3'RR-peaks led to a slight reduction in BCR expression in SUDHL4, but not in the other cell lines (Figure 4B-C and Supplementary Figure 6B-C).

IGH enhancers are active only in B cells. Therefore, no effect should be observed upon targeting them in non-B cells. In addition, based on the results of BCR expression, we expected that our CRISPRi approach would affect growth of B cells without IGH translocations only if they depended on BCR signaling and the E μ enhancer was targeted. To test this, we assessed cell growth and BCR expression in 1) BL cell lines with MYC-IGL t(8;22) translocation (BL2, BL60); 2) BL cell lines with MYC-IGK t(2;8) translocation (JI, LY91); 3) B-cell cell line without MYC translocation (P493-6); 4) embryonic kidney HEK293T cell line. We observed reduced cell growth in BL2, BL60 and P493-6 cells transduced with sgRNA targeting the E μ peak. JI and LY91 cells did not respond to any construct, neither did HEK293T cells where IGH enhancers not active (Supplementary Figure 9A-D). In line with this, JI and LY91 cells are BCR-negative, they do not express neither IgM nor IgG (data not shown). BL2, BL60 and P493-6 cells express surface IgM and we observed a 20-30% (BL2), 40-70% (BL60) and 82-85% (P493-6) decrease in IgM-positive cells upon targeting the E μ peak (Supplementary Figure 9E). This confirmed that while the effect of silencing of the E μ enhancer may

be attributed to interfering with both the oncogene expression and BCR, reduced cell growth observed upon 3'RR targeting is not related to the BCR signaling.

MYC overexpression rescues cell proliferation in Burkitt lymphoma cell line upon *IGH* enhancer inhibition

Since we observed a significant decrease in cell growth accompanied by MYC downregulation in DG75 upon blocking of *IGH* enhancers, we determined whether MYC overexpression could rescue the phenotype (Figure 5A). To this end we generated a DG75 cell line with a doxycycline-inducible MYC expression (DG75-MYC-OE, Supplementary Figure 10A). As control, cells with empty vector (DG75-EV) were used. Induction of MYC expression was tested on both RNA and protein level (Supplementary Figure 10B-C) with doxycycline doses 0.1-0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Survival of DG75-MYC-OE cells upon induction of MYC expression was determined over a course of 3 weeks (Supplementary Figure 10D). We established that the use of 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ is sufficient for MYC overexpression, while higher doses caused a strong decrease in cell survival. Next, DG75-MYC-OE and DG75-MYC-EV cells were transduced with the set of sgRNAs targeting *IGH* enhancers peaks and non-targeting controls and their viability was tested. We observed a partial rescue of the effect exerted by inhibition of *IGH* enhancers in DG75-MYC-OE cells upon MYC induction (Figure 5B), but not in DG75-EV (Figure 5C). Although we could not fully rescue the observed effects on viability upon targeting *IGH* enhancers, our results suggest that the observed negative effect is at least in part caused by downregulation of MYC.

Discussion

In NHL, recurrent chromosomal translocations are known to bring oncogenes under the regulation of *IGH* enhancers – 5' intronic E μ and 3'regulatory regions, 3'RR1 and 3'RR2. Up to date, targeting of *IGH* enhancers as therapeutic options remains elusive. Therefore, delineation of the core *IGH* enhancers regions, which control the expression of translocated oncogenes, as well as growth and survival of lymphoma cells is of a key importance. Our study is the first to define the exact regions crucial for survival of NHL. The use of a saturating CRISPRi library allowed us to target and thoroughly screen the *IGH* enhancers. Interestingly, survival of lymphoma cells upon blocking of *IGH* enhancers core regions varied between cell lines. Taking into account that chromosomal translocations can occur at various regions within the *IGH* locus, our data suggest that the observed patterns are connected to the breakpoint sites.

In DG75, SUDHL4 and WSU-DLCL2, both the E μ enhancer and 3'RRs are involved in the translocation. We observed consistent downregulation of the translocated oncogene (MYC or BCL2) upon

blocking *IGH* enhancers, with a similar effect for each of the identified essential regions. This may indicate a cooperation between *IGH* enhancers in driving expression of the translocated oncogene. Spatial interaction between E μ and 3'RR occurs for example during *IGH* locus rearrangements²⁶. Ghazzaoui et al.²⁷ developed several mouse models of c-myc knock-in juxtaposed with *IGH* enhancers and demonstrated that the dynamics of lymphoma development and mice survival varied, depending on the oncogene insertion site. The shortest lifespan was observed when both E μ and 3'RR enhancers were involved. They concluded that E μ and 3'RR enhancers cooperate in driving translocated oncogenes expression and lymphomagenesis. We tested in our study whether inhibition of one core *IGH* enhancer region affects transcription of others, but we did not observe any consistent effect on eRNAs expression from 3'RR when blocking E μ and *vice versa* (data not shown).

In BL cell lines BL41, CA46 and ST486 the intronic E μ is not involved in the translocation with MYC. In agreement with this, we observed little to no MYC downregulation upon targeting of the E μ enhancer essential region. In contrast, blocking of 3'RRs core regions in BL41 and CA46 had a significant effect on MYC transcript levels as well as cell survival. In NHLs, despite differences in the location of the breakpoint in *IGH*, the 3'RR always remains in the *IGH* locus. This regulatory region was suggested previously to be a good target for therapy^{28,29} and was found sufficient to deregulate oncogene expression^{7,27}. So far, several factors were shown to affect transcriptional activity of 3'RR, proving that this enhancer may be druggable³⁰⁻³². The 3'RRs span 25-30 kb each, therefore it is necessary to further pinpoint what sites to target. In mice, HS3a and HS1.2 were shown to be important for deregulation of the translocated MYC³³. Our approach revealed HS4 (peak1) and HS1.2 (peak2) within 3'RRs as crucial for human B-cell lymphoma cells survival. Importantly, P493-6 cell line was not affected by blocking of 3'RRs, in contrast to E μ . This suggests that the 3'RR-peaks identified by us are attractive candidates for therapeutic targeting. However, it still need to be determined whether inhibition of HS4 and HS1.2 is toxic specifically for *IGH*-translocation positive lymphomas and not normal B cells.

ST486 cells exhibited resistance to inhibition of *IGH* core enhancers regions. This cell line bears several translocations involving MYC: typical BL reciprocal translocation MYC/*IGH* t(8;14)(q24;q32) but also complex t(8;14;18)(q24;q32;q23)³⁴. This leads to the presence of MYC at as many as four different locations: chromosome 8, der(8), der(14) and der(18). Probably downregulation of MYC expression from only one site was not enough to observe a significant change in overall levels, nor a more profound effect on cell proliferation.

We were able to partially rescue the phenotype of blocking *IGH* enhancers by MYC overexpression in a BL cell line. This suggests that other elements controlled by *IGH* enhancers may be involved. Most

lymphoma cells retain expression of BCR from the non-translocated *IGH* allele. In our approach, sgRNAs for *IGH* enhancer-essential regions can target both alleles. We observed partial BCR loss upon blocking of the E μ -peak in nearly all tested lymphoma cell lines with *IGH* translocations but also in BL cells with *IgL* translocations and in P493-6 B cell line which does not harbor any *IG* translocation. In contrast, targeting 3'RR-peaks in general did not affect BCR expression. This is in line with previous studies showing a reduction of IgM and IgG expressing B cells in mice with deletion of the E μ enhancer^{8,35-37}. On the other hand, singular deletions of 3'RR enhancer components in mice were not sufficient³⁸⁻⁴¹ and only combinatorial deletion of HS4 and HS3b downregulated BCR in B-cells^{42,43}. However, other studies showed that deletion of HS3b and HS4 or even the whole 3'RR did not affect surface IgM, only IgG was reduced^{29,44-46}. Interestingly, it has been shown that while BCR ablation per se does not negatively influence lymphoma growth, BCR-negative BL cells are outcompeted by their BCR-expressing counterparts⁴⁷. This is similar to the effect on cell survival observed by us upon E μ -peak inhibition in the GFP-growth competition assays. Taken together, our results indicate that the reduced cell growth observed upon inhibition of essential *IGH* enhancer regions can be attributed to downregulation of oncogene expression and in case of the E μ – also to the loss of BCR.

Current knowledge regarding the function of eRNAs in NHL is very limited. Recently, a B-cell specific eRNA AL928768.3 was shown to regulate MYC expression in BL¹². This eRNA resides within human 3'RR1 region (hg19, chr14:106170301-10617093). Authors modulated the expression of AL928768.3 by either siRNA-mediated knock-down or overexpression, and observed down- and upregulation of MYC, respectively. The effect on MYC was specific to cells bearing *MYC/IGH* translocation. Knock-down of eRNA AL928768.3 resulted in a decrease in BL cell proliferation. Verification of this observation in a wider panel of NHL would be of interest. In our screen, inhibition of AL928768.3 region with CRISPR/dCas9 had in general no significant impact on cell survival overall; however a few individual sgRNAs were strongly depleted, especially in DG75 and SUDHL4 (Supplementary Table 6). Here, we confirmed transcription from core *IGH* enhancers regions and validated arising eRNAs in a panel of B-cell lymphomas, both NHL and HL, as well as NHL patient-derived samples. It was shown that the activity of *IGH* enhancers depends on transcription factors such as e.g. BOB.1 and PU.1⁴⁸. Low expression of *IGH* eRNAs in HL is in line with absence of those transcription factors^{48,49}. Levels of BOB.1 and PU.1 are high in BL and germinal center B cells but variable in DLBCL^{48,49}, which may account for the observed differences.

Blocking transcription of the essential regions with CRISPRi resulted in downregulation of eRNAs derived from them, which was accompanied by oncogene and BCR downregulation. Whether *IGH* eRNAs from core regions are indeed involved in the regulation of those translocated oncogenes and BCR requires

further study. For some eRNAs the very act of their transcription and not necessarily the transcript itself is important for carrying out their function^{9,50}. On the other hand, enhancer RNAs may help achieve proper chromatin conformation and recruit transcriptional machinery to target regions⁵¹. Transcription of 3'RR in mice was shown to recruit activation-induced cytidine deaminase, which leads to *IGH* locus suicide recombination and BCR loss, potentially contributing to B-cell homeostasis¹⁰. eRNAs can also interact with other classes of non-coding RNAs. Long non-coding RNA CSR (lncRNA-CSR) interacts with 3'RR's HS4 eRNA, which promotes CSR⁵². Apart from these functions in chromatin, the role of eRNAs in the cytoplasm has also been reported⁵³. We observed a predominant cytoplasmic localization of the eRNA from 3'RR-peak 1 which suggest that it may have additional role beyond acting *in cis* in the *IGH* locus. So far, we were not able to efficiently knock down *IGH* eRNAs with the use of either Gapmers or shRNAs, therefore the potential role of *IGH* eRNAs requires further investigation.

A more detailed analysis of the *IGH* enhancers core regions would be of interest. Enhancers are known to be packed with transcription factors binding sites. Elucidation if and how their binding is affected upon blocking of essential enhancer sites will help understand expression regulation at those regions. In addition, E μ and 3'RRs can form chromatin loops, so a closer look at the chromatin architecture in the *IGH* locus upon blocking of the core enhancer regions could provide insights into the mechanisms involved. Inhibition of the *IGH* enhancers allows for a precise, B-cell restricted, targeting of translocated oncogenes in B-cell lymphoma. This makes the core regions identified by us attractive targets for therapeutic approaches. So far, HDAC inhibitors and aryl hydrocarbon receptor ligands have been shown to affect activity of the 3'RR and *IGH* transcription^{30,31}. However, their effect on lymphomas driven by *IGH* translocations has not been evaluated. Recently, a small molecule reducing the activity of the E μ has been reported, with an inhibitory effect on growth of *IGH* translocation positive multiple myeloma cells *in vitro* and *in vivo*⁵⁴. However, we showed that this compound is also toxic to other cell types³².

In summary, we pinpointed regions within *IGH* enhancers E μ and 3'RR crucial for survival of B-cell lymphomas. We showed that the observed negative effect on cell survival is likely to be attributed to downregulation of translocated oncogenes and in case of E μ inhibition also to BCR loss. Our results set a frame for further studies to explore the therapeutic potential of inhibiting *IGH* enhancers in B-cell lymphoma.

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A. Human, *IGH* locus, chr14

B.

Region	Localization (hg19)	Number of sgRNAs	Mean distance	Median distance	Min distance	Max distance
E μ	chr14:106322800-106331124	2219	8.1	4	1	302
3'RR1	chr14:106145100-106176250	3784	10.7	4	1	1850
3'RR2	chr14:106024800-106050011	3322	10.6	4	1	1285

C.

D.

Figure 1. Design and generation of a tiling CRISPRi library targeting *IGH* enhancers. **A.** Scheme of the human *IGH* locus. Green - *IGH* enhancers: two 3' regulatory regions (3'RR), which are composed of smaller enhancers (HS) and the intronic enhancer E μ , composed of the core and two matrix attachment regions (MAR); black - immunoglobulin genes: C - constant, J - joining, D - diverse, V - variable. **B.** Summary of the sgRNA distribution in the CRISPR-eIGH library. Note that since 3'RR1 and 3'RR2 are highly similar, 2344 sgRNAs are common for both regions. **C.** SgRNA abundance in the CRISPR-eIGH library obtained with NGS. Red dotted lines indicate the 10th (left) and 90th (right) percentile. **D.** Overview of the CRISPRi screen experiment.

Figure 2. Tiling CRISPRi screen of the *IGH* enhancers in B-cell non-Hodgkin lymphoma cells. A. CRISPRi screen results. Scatterplots represent change of sgRNAs abundance relative to the initial pool in two screen replicates for each cell line. Numbers in the bottom left corner indicate the total number of sgRNA in the given cell line that were consistently >2-fold depleted from the initial pool. Black – sgRNAs targeting *IGH* enhancers, grey – non-targeting controls, red – positive controls targeting CD79. **B.** Fold change values of 20 consecutive sgRNA calculated using the sliding window approach. Colored boxes mark regions identified as essential for cell survival. For $E\mu$: chr14:106328838-106329184, pink box, 3'RR1 and 3'RR2: chr14:106152156-106153203 and chr14:106032312-106033352, blue box – peak 1, chr14:106162681-106163347 and chr14:106041116-106041795, green box – peak 2. **C-D.** GFP growth competition

assay. Assay performed with individual sgRNAs over the course of 3 weeks in **C. BL** and **D. DLBCL** cell lines. Average and standard deviation from 3 independent biological replicates is shown. *, $P \leq 0.05$, **, $P \leq 0.01$, ***, $P \leq 0.001$, mixed model analysis. **E.** Localization of breakpoints in the *IGH* locus for cell lines used in this study. Red – BL cell lines, purple – DLBCL cell lines.

Figure 3. Transcriptional activity of *IGH* enhancers. **A.** Chromatin-enriched RNA-Seq results for *IGH* enhancer regions accompanied by UCSC tracks from GM12878 B-cells: transcription and histone marks: H3K4me1 and H3K27ac – characteristic for enhancer regions and H3K4me3 – characteristic for promoters and active genes. Red – indicates reads from the plus strand, blue – indicates reads from the minus strand. Pink - $E\mu$ peak, blue – 3'RRs peak 1, green – 3'RRs peak 2. **B.** Cellular localization of eRNA transcripts determined by cellular fractionation. Average and standard deviation from two biological replicates are shown. **C-D.** Validation of eRNA expression **C.** in a panel of B-cell lymphoma cell lines and control B cells: BL n=9, DLBCL n=12: ACB n=5, GCB n=7, HL n=8, control (germinal center B-cells) n=4. Expression normalized to TBP. ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's Multiple Comparison Post-Test was applied; *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$; ***, $P \leq 0.001$ **D.** in patient-derived FFPE samples: BL n=8, DLBCL n=13: ABC n=7, GCB n=6, control (healthy donor tonsil) n=6. Expression normalized to TBP. ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's Multiple Comparison Post-Test was applied; *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$.

Figure 4. Downstream effects of targeting *IGH* enhancers. **A.** Expression of oncogenes involved in *IGH* translocation – MYC (DG75, BL41) or BCL2 (SUDHL4) and expression of eRNAs upon blocking of *IGH* enhancers essential regions on RNA level determined by qRT-PCR. Mean and SD of three independent biological replicates are shown. Expression normalized to HPRT. *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$, ***, $P \leq 0.001$, Mann-Whitney test. **B.** Immunostaining of B-cell receptor (BCR) on cell surface in DG75, BL41 (IgM) and SUDHL4 (IgG). Representative histograms of overlaid data for non-targeting controls (grey) and sgRNAs targeting *IGH*-enhancers essential regions (pink, E μ peak; blue, 3'RR peak 1; green, 3'RR peak 2). Arrows indicate samples from a separate staining in SUDHL4. **C.** Average and SD of percentage of BCR-positive cells (surface IgM or IgG) from two biological replicates. *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$; ***, $P \leq 0.001$; ****, $P \leq 0.001$, Student's two-tailed t-test.

Figure 5. MYC overexpression rescues cell viability in BL cell line DG75 upon inhibition of *IGH* enhancer-essential regions. **A.** Overview of the MYC-rescue experiment. **B. and C.** Viability of **B.** DG75-MYC OE cell line and **C.** Control cell line DG75-EV transduced with sgRNAs targeting *IGH* enhancers and treated/untreated with doxycycline for induction of MYC expression. Average and SD from three independent biological replicates are shown. *, $P \leq 0.05$; **, $P \leq 0.01$, Student's t-test.